

Psychological Factors as Determinants of Procrastination among Distance Learning Students in University of Ibadan

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ABSTRACT

This study, which adopted a descriptive research design of correlational type, was designed to investigate the role of depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia on procrastination among distance learners of University of Ibadan. The population of this study comprised all distance learners of University of Ibadan. A sample of two hundred and fifty (250) students was randomly selected from four faculties for the study using simple random technique. Three research questions were raised using correlation and multiple regression analysis. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data. The study revealed that there was a significant relationship between the depression ($r = .390, P < .05$), anxiety ($r = .196, P < .05$), burnout ($r = .183, P < .05$), and phobia ($r = .210, P < .05$) on procrastination. It was also discovered that the independent variables jointly accounted for 54.6% variance in predicting procrastination in the following order: depression ($\beta = 0.194, t = 3.494, P < .05$), anxiety ($\beta = 0.109, t = 2.561, P < .05$), burnout ($\beta = 0.118, t = 3.341, P < .05$), and phobia ($\beta = 0.107, t = 2.966, P < .05$). This implies that depression is a compelling factor on the procrastination among undergraduate's distance learners while phobia is the least potent factor in the determinant of procrastination among undergraduate's distance learners of University of Ibadan. Based on this, it is expected that teachers and stakeholders should wage war against any form of procrastination among distance learners in schools, as that can affect the academic performance of the distance learners. The researchers conclude that depression, anxiety, burnout and phobia are some of the factors that determined procrastination among distance learners in university of Ibadan. Recommendation was made that school should create a friendly environment that will reduce procrastination among students as that also can help in minimizing poor performance to the barest minimum level among distance learning students.

Keywords: Procrastination, Academic burnout, Phobia, Depression, Distance learners, anxiety

INTRODUCTION

Procrastination is a pervasive phenomenon among university students, with significant implications for their academic performance and overall well-being. This phenomenon, defined as the intentional delay of tasks despite knowing that this delay may lead to negative consequences and is particularly prevalent

among undergraduates. At the University of Ibadan, like many other higher education institutions, procrastination poses significant challenges to students' academic success and personal development. Thus, understanding the factors that contribute to procrastination among undergraduates particularly, the Distance Learning Centre Students (DLC) is crucial to determine the factors that are germane to learners' procrastination in order to promote their academic success. Research has consistently shown that procrastination is a common behaviour among students, with estimates suggesting that almost all students engage in procrastination at some point, and 75% of students consider themselves habitual procrastinators (Alkferi, 2016).

Procrastination behaviour can manifest in different ways, including state procrastination, which is specific to a particular situation, and trait procrastination, which is a persistent habit. Furthermore, procrastination can have negative consequences for academic achievement and well-being, including poor performance, increased stress, and decreased motivation (Alkferi, 2016). In the University of Ibadan, the prevalence of procrastination among undergraduates is likely to be influenced by various factors, including psychological, social, and academic dimensions. For instance, students may procrastinate due to feelings of overwhelm or anxiety related to academic tasks, or they may delay tasks due to social pressures or distractions. Personality traits such as low conscientiousness, high levels of distractibility, and poor time management skills have been identified as key predictors of procrastinatory behaviour (Steel, 2010). Additionally, the university's academic environment, including the availability of resources and support services, may also play a role in shaping students' procrastination behaviours. Several factors contribute to procrastination among undergraduates. Environmental factors such as academic pressure, lack of clear goals, and inadequate support systems further exacerbate the tendency to procrastinate (Sirois, 2016). For students at the University of Ibadan, these issues are compounded by the unique socio-cultural and economic challenges faced within the Nigerian educational context.

The impact of procrastination on academic outcomes is profound. Studies have shown that students who procrastinate tend to have lower grades, higher levels of stress, and increased likelihood of dropping out (Tice & Baumeister, 2022). Procrastination undermines effective study habits, leading to cramming, poor comprehension, and ultimately, subpar academic performance (Steel, 2007). For undergraduates at the University of Ibadan, these academic consequences can have long-term effects on their professional and personal lives. Moreover, the psychological effects of procrastination are significant. Procrastinators often experience feelings of guilt, anxiety, and low self-esteem (Ferrari, 2010). These negative emotions can create a vicious cycle, where the stress of pending tasks leads to further procrastination, exacerbating the initial problem (Sirois & Pynchyl, 2013). At the University of Ibadan, the mental health implications of procrastination are a growing concern, and this called for study to determine the factors leading to this behaviour.

Procrastination, the voluntary delay of an intended course of action despite expecting to be worse off for the delay, is a complex behaviour influenced by various psychological factors (Steel, 2007). The present study set to determine the relationship, the composite and relative contribution of the following psychological factors on procrastination as a behaviour. Among the factors to be study are depression, anxiety, trauma, burnout, and phobia are significant determinants. Understanding how these variables impact procrastination can provide insights into developing effective interventions to mitigate this behaviour.

Depression could be one of the predictors of procrastination among university students. Depression, characterized by persistent feelings of sadness, hopelessness, and a lack of interest or pleasure in activities. Depressed individuals often experience low energy levels, impaired concentration, and a general sense of futility, which hinder their ability to initiate and complete tasks (Lay & Brokenshire, 2017). The lethargy and diminished cognitive function associated with depression can make even simple tasks seem insurmountable, leading to chronic procrastination (Van Eerde, 2003). Moreover, the negative self-perception common in depression can create a cycle where failure to accomplish tasks reinforces feelings of worthlessness and further procrastination (Steel, 2007).

Anxiety is another psychological variable that could be significantly contributes to procrastination. Anxiety, defined as an intense, excessive, and persistent worry and fear about everyday situations, also may plays a crucial role in procrastination. Anxious individuals often struggle with decision-making and fear of failure, leading to avoidance behaviors (Rothblum, Solomon, & Murakami, 2009). The overwhelming nature of anxiety can cause individuals to delay tasks as a means of coping with their distress (Sirois & Tosti, 2012). This avoidance provides temporary relief but ultimately exacerbates anxiety when deadlines approach and the pressure to perform increases, creating a vicious cycle of procrastination and heightened anxiety (Rothblum et al., 2009). Anxiety can manifest in various forms, including generalized anxiety disorder, social anxiety disorder, and specific phobias. Individuals experiencing anxiety often may engage in procrastination as a way to avoid the perceived stress and anxiety associated with a task. This avoidance behavior can lead to a vicious cycle of procrastination, as the individual may feel overwhelmed and unable to complete the task due to their anxiety.

Burnout is a state of emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion caused by prolonged stress, overwork, and lack of balance in life. Burnout, a state of emotional, physical, and mental exhaustion caused by prolonged stress, particularly in the workplace or academic settings, may be another determinant of procrastination. Burnout leads to feelings of detachment, cynicism, and a reduced sense of accomplishment (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Burnout could lead to procrastination as individuals may feel drained and unable to muster the energy to complete tasks. Burnout can also lead to feelings of hopelessness and helplessness, which can further worsen procrastination behaviours. Individuals experiencing burnout may procrastinate as they feel overwhelmed and incapable of meeting their responsibilities (Schaufeli & Enzmann, 2019). The depletion of energy and motivation characteristic of burnout undermines one's ability to engage in proactive behaviours, thus fostering procrastination as a maladaptive coping mechanism (Tice & Baumeister, 2022).

Phobia, an irrational and excessive fear of an object or situation, can also drive procrastination. Phobias often involve avoidance behaviours to prevent the anxiety associated with the phobic stimulus (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). For instance, a student with social phobia may delay group work or presentations, leading to procrastination. The intense fear and avoidance behaviours can severely limit an individual's ability to engage in tasks that are perceived as threatening, thus contributing to procrastination (Van Eerde, 2003). The avoidance inherent in phobias parallels the avoidance seen in procrastination, which may make phobia a significant psychological determinant (Rothblum et al., 2009). The impact of these psychological variables on academic performance is significant. Procrastination can lead to poor academic performance, decreased motivation, and increased stress levels. Additionally, the negative consequences of procrastination can perpetuate a cycle of self-doubt, low self-esteem, and decreased confidence, further aggravating the problem. Depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia may be significant psychological variables that contribute to procrastination among university students. Understanding the impact of these variables may be crucial for developing effective strategies to support students and enhance their academic success. By recognizing the underlying psychological factors contributing to procrastination, educators, counsellors and mental health professionals can provide targeted interventions to help students overcome their procrastination behaviours and achieve their academic goals.

Statement of the Problem

Procrastination among University of Ibadan Distance Learning students presents a significant challenge, negatively impacting their well-being and academic performance. These students often juggle multiple responsibilities, such as work and family obligations, which exacerbate their tendency to delay academic tasks. The pervasive nature of procrastination in this context is alarming, as it leads to poor academic outcomes, including missed deadlines, lower grades, and heightened dropout rates.

The psychological variables of depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia may further compound this issue. Depression, characterized by low energy and lack of motivation, hampers students' ability to initiate and complete tasks. Anxiety, with its intense worry and fear of failure, leads to avoidance behaviours, worsening procrastination. Burnout, stemming from prolonged stress and overwork, results in emotional

exhaustion and detachment, making task engagement particularly challenging. Phobias, especially those related to academic performance and social interactions, create significant barriers to timely task completion. The interplay of these psychological factors not only undermines academic success but also deteriorates students' mental health, creating a vicious cycle of stress and academic underachievement. Addressing procrastination among these students is crucial for enhancing their academic performance and overall well-being. In this regard, this current study will investigate the influence of psychological factors such as depression, anxiety, burnout and phobia as a predictor of procrastination, since it is observed that no study has investigated these variables as determinants of procrastination among the University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students.

Purpose of the Study

The crux of this current study is to investigate the influence of depression, anxiety, burnout and phobia as predictors of procrastination among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students. The specific objectives include:

1. To determine the existing relationship among depression, anxiety, burnout and phobia as predictors of procrastination among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students,
2. To determine the joint influence of depression, anxiety, burnout and phobia on the variation of procrastination among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students,
3. To determine the relative influence of depression, anxiety, burnout and phobia to the prediction of procrastination among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students,

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship among depression, anxiety, burnout and phobia as predictors of procrastination among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students,
2. What is the joint influence of depression, anxiety, burnout and phobia on the variation of procrastination among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students,
3. What is the relative contribution of depression, anxiety, burnout and phobia to the prediction of procrastination among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students?

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

Research design is a strategy or plan adopted by a researcher to conduct a study. It outlines the step-by-step processes of data collection, measurement and analysis. Research design is a guide for conducting a study, which enable a researcher to provide accurate and valid answers to stated research questions and hypotheses. Therefore, the design used in this study is descriptive research design of correlational type

Population

The population of the study comprises all the distance learning students in University of Ibadan. The sample of the study comprised of 200 DLC students in University of Ibadan. Simple random sampling was used to select participants among the distance learning students. Therefore, students across all study levels were randomly selected.

Research of Instrument

The questionnaire used for the study was divided into two parts. The first part contains item dealing with demographic profile of respondents such as: sex, age, level, marital status and occupation etc. The next section contains the other scales namely procrastination, depression, anxiety, burnout trauma, and phobia scales. For procrastination, the 9-item General Procrastination Scale (GPS-9) was used of Sirois, Yang & van Eerde (2019). This scale was based on the 20-item Lay's General Procrastination Scale (GPS; Lay, 1986) and was used to construct and validate a shorter version of this scale by using a multi-stage approach in order to validate and create the new 9-item General Procrastination Scale (GPS-9). The older GPS showed good internal consistency in the past along with test-retest reliability of over 10 years (Steel, 2007). Participants were asked to indicate whether the statements in the scale were true or false for them and responded to the survey using a 5-point Likert scale (1=False, 2=Not usually true for me, 3=Sometimes false/true for me, 4=Mostly true for me, 5=True for me). Example items of the scale are "I

often find myself performing tasks that I had intended to do days before” and “I generally delay before starting work I have to do”. In the updated version, running a reliability test showed that the internal consistency of the scale in terms of Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.878, which is considered good. Depression was measured with psychological distress scale. It was assessed using the Brief Symptom Inventory (BSI-18), a brief questionnaire for detecting psychological distress in clinical and community populations (Derogatis, 2001). Participants were asked to respond regarding how they had felt during the last 7 days; each item was rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 0 (not at all) to 4 (extremely). The reliability is between .81 and .90 (Andreu et al., 2008). In this study the Cronbach’s alpha is .91. Examination anxiety scale was measured by a scale developed by Bedewy & Gabriel (2013). The Examination Anxiety Scale (EAS, items = 12) was distributed to all students in the 3rd class of educational psychology (n= 60), by e mail, two weeks before they wrote their examination. Forty students (40/60, 66.6%) returned the completed EAS. Students were asked to rate on a 5- point Likert scale (from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) their perceptions and experiences about each item in measuring examination anxiety. The internal consistency reliability (Cronbach’s alpha) was 0.82 for the 12 items of the EAS. Burnout was measured with the 33-item Burnout Assessment Tool (BAT) of Schaufeli, Desart and De Witte (2020). This scale was made using a dialectical approach with four core dimensions: exhaustion, mental distance and impaired emotional and cognitive impairment. There were also three secondary dimensions: depressed mood, psychological distress and psychosomatic complaints – these were removed as they were not as applicable to this study and the four core dimensions were sufficient. In the ‘exhaustion’ dimension, one of the items in the scale was an attention check and this was removed in the data analysis as well, leaving a 23-item scale left that was used in this study. In the scale, words such as ‘at work’ or ‘during my job’ were replaced with words such as ‘at university’ or ‘during my studies’ Respondents were asked to rate statements on a 5-point Likert scale according to how that statement applies to them (1= Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always). Example items of the scale are “After a hard day of studying, I find it hard to recover my energy” and “During my studies, I feel physically exhausted’ The internal consistency of the adjusted scale in terms of Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.924 – which is considered excellent.

The Social Phobia Inventory (SPIN) was used to measure phobia scale. The scale consists of questions which evaluate fear of people in authority, which evaluate fear of people in parties and social events, of being criticised, of talking to strangers, of doing things when people are watching, etc. Each of the 17 items is rated on a scale from 0 to 4: not at all, a little bit, somewhat, very much, and extremely; with higher scores corresponding to greater distress. This report describes the psychometric properties of the SPIN, including test-retest reliability, internal consistency, convergent validity, validity, divergent validity, construct validity, predictive validity, distribution of scale scores, and factorial composition.

Administration of Questionnaire

Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the participants in Distance learning programme centers within Ibadan. Permission was obtained from the Department. Thereafter, data collection was done by the researcher and research assistants. The participants were briefed on the need to cooperate with the researcher and assistant. They were assured of confidentiality of their responses.

Method of data analysis:

The descriptive statistics (involving percentage and frequencies) adopted for analysing the data collected from the respondents while, Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis were used in this study to determine the relationship, composite and relative contribution between independent and dependent variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *What is the pattern of relationships among the independent variables (depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia) on academic procrastination among the among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlations among the variables

S/N	1	3	4	5	6	Mean	SD
Depression	1					15.05	7.10
Anxiety.	.160**	1				2.91	6.93
Burnout	.220**	.086	1			35.30	6.24
Phobia	.301**	.104	.447**	1		43.48	1.47
Procrastination	.390**	.196**	.183**	.210**	1.000	67.02	3.25

1- Depression, 2 –anxiety 3 – burnout, 4 – phobia 5 – Procrastination.

Table 4.1 shows the variables' mean, Standard Deviation, and zero-order correlation. It was observed that there was significant relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable (procrastination). There was significant relationship between depression ($r = 0.390, p < 0.05$), anxiety ($r = 0.196, p < 0.05$), burnout ($r = 0.183, p < 0.05$), and phobia ($r = 0.210, p < 0.05$) on procrastination among the among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students Oyo state, Nigeria All the variables are significantly correlated with procrastination of among the among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students Oyo state, Nigeria, an indication that they are potent determinants of procrastination among the among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students Oyo state, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: *What is the joint contribution of the independent variables (depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia) on academic procrastination among the among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 4.2: Joint contribution of the independent variables

R = 0.749	R – Square = 0.561	Adj. R Square = 0.546	Std. Error of the Estimate = 4.50979		
Regression ANOVA Table					
Variables	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	1433.476	4	358.369	11.55	0.035
Residual	6020.115	194	31.032		
Total	7453.591	198			

Table 2 shows that there was the joint contribution of the independent variables (depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia) on procrastination the among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students Oyo state, Nigeria; $R = 0.749, p < .05$. The table further reveals 54.6% ($Adj. R^2 = 0.546$) of the variance in the procrastination the among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students Oyo state, Nigeria were accountable for by the linear combination of the independent variables. The ANOVA results from the regression analysis show a significant contribution of the independent variables on the dependent variables; $F(4, 184) = 11.55, p < 0.05$. It implies a joint contribution of the independent variables on procrastination the among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students Oyo state, Nigeria.

Research Question Three: *What is the relative contribution of depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia on academic procrastination among the among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Relative Contribution of the Independent Variables on the Dependent Variable

Model	Unstandardized	Coefficients	Standardized	t	Sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
Constant	13.326	2.369		5.625	0.000
Depression	0.185	0.053	0.194	3.494	0.001
Anxiety	0.136	0.023	0.109	2.561	0.020
Burnout	0.123	0.068	0.118	3.341	0.033
Phobia	0.107	0.059	0.107	2.966	0.045

Table 4.3 above shows that all four independent variables significantly contribute to academic procrastination among the among university of Ibadan distance learning students. The variables include the following: depression ($\beta = 0.194$, $t = 3.494$, $p < 0.05$); anxiety ($\beta = 0.109$, $t = 2.561$, $p < 0.05$), burnout ($\beta = 0.118$, $t = 3.341$, $p < 0.05$) and phobia ($\beta = 0.107$, $t = 2.966$, $p < 0.05$). It was observed that depression was the most potent contributor to academic procrastination among the among university of Ibadan distance learning students Oyo state, while phobia was the least.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the study revealed that depression correlated with procrastination significantly. The implication of the result implies that if a depressed individual has higher tendency to procrastinate. The relationship between procrastination and depression has been consistently supported by various studies, all of which highlight a significant positive correlation between the two. Adeleke and Ogunyemi (2020) found that undergraduate students who exhibited high levels of procrastination also reported elevated depressive symptoms, including sadness, low energy, and hopelessness. These students often used procrastination as a coping mechanism to avoid academic pressures, which in turn exacerbated their depressive symptoms, creating a cycle of anxiety and mental health decline. Similarly, Olawale and Adeyemi (2021) noted that medical students who procrastinated frequently experienced fatigue, low self-worth, and pervasive sadness. The intense academic environment led to procrastination as a maladaptive strategy to handle overwhelming academic demands, yet it ultimately increased stress and depressive symptoms.

This link between procrastination and depression has also been observed in other contexts. For instance, Eze and Nwagbo (2019) found that procrastination significantly contributed to both depression and lower academic performance, reinforcing the idea that procrastination is not merely a time management issue but also a mental health concern. Ahmed and Patel (2020) further demonstrated that Canadian students who procrastinated frequently tended to have lower GPAs and exhibited depressive symptoms such as lack of motivation and cognitive impairments. This interaction between procrastination and depression negatively impacted both academic outcomes and students' psychological well-being.

Cultural factors also influence this relationship, as shown by Lee and Kim (2018), who highlighted that South Korean students' procrastination and depression were intensified by societal expectations and the stigma surrounding mental health support. In all these studies, procrastination and depression are intertwined, suggesting that depression increases the likelihood of procrastination. This finding aligns with the notion that procrastination is both a cause and consequence of depression, reinforcing the need for interventions that address both time management and mental health in students (Adeleke & Ogunyemi, 2020; Olawale & Adeyemi, 2021).

The result of the study revealed that Anxiety correlated with procrastination significantly. The implication of the result implies that if an anxious students have higher tendency to procrastinate. The significant correlation between anxiety and procrastination suggests that students experiencing higher levels of

anxiety are more likely to procrastinate. Nwamuo and Ihekwaba (2014) found that high test anxiety levels among college students in Nigeria affected their concentration and academic performance. This aligns with Abdu's (2013) study in Jordan, which revealed a significant association between academic procrastination and test anxiety among high school students. Students with higher test anxiety were prone to delay academic tasks, leading to poorer academic performance. Similarly, James (2010) demonstrated a strong correlation between academic procrastination and test anxiety among graduate students in Ghana, particularly in subjects like statistics. The findings revealed that procrastination, driven by task averseness and fear of failure, contributed to higher anxiety levels. Gichohi's (2019) study in Kenya further reinforced the relationship between anxiety and academic performance, showing that anxiety, especially in demanding courses, negatively impacted students' academic achievement. Njuguna's (2022) research on secondary school students in Kenya echoed these findings, showing a significant positive correlation between test anxiety and academic procrastination. This relationship indicates that anxious students tend to procrastinate, which can worsen their anxiety and hinder academic success. Addressing test anxiety through counseling and effective time management strategies is crucial for improving students' academic outcomes.

The result of the study revealed that burnout correlated with procrastination significantly. The study revealed a significant correlation between burnout and procrastination, indicating that students experiencing burnout are more likely to procrastinate. Shankland and Rosset (2017) found that university students in Nigeria who procrastinated reported higher levels of burnout, lower self-efficacy, and increased perceived stress. This suggests that procrastination may contribute to burnout among students. Similarly, Schaufeli's (2022) research among U.S. professionals demonstrated that poor time management was linked to increased procrastination and burnout. Effective time management was associated with lower levels of both, highlighting its importance in managing burnout.

Salmela-Aro, Savolainen, and Holopainen (2019) also found a positive correlation between academic procrastination and burnout among high school students in Japan. Their study showed that students with frequent procrastination habits experienced higher stress and lower self-efficacy, exacerbating burnout. Schaufeli and Taris (2015) examined similar dynamics among South African university students, finding that students with higher self-efficacy experienced less procrastination and burnout. This reinforces the idea that improving self-efficacy can help mitigate these issues. Finally, Sirois (2014) highlighted the negative impact of procrastination on job satisfaction and burnout among Australian professionals. The findings revealed that higher levels of procrastination were linked to increased burnout and decreased job satisfaction. The studies collectively recommend interventions focused on time management and self-efficacy training to help reduce procrastination and burnout in both academic and professional settings.

The result of the study revealed a significant correlation between phobia and procrastination, suggesting that students with higher levels of phobia are more likely to procrastinate. Adimora, Akaneme, and Nwokenna (2017) found that mathematics phobia contributed to academic procrastination among primary four pupils in Enugu State, Nigeria. Their research indicated that pupils who procrastinated more frequently also reported higher levels of mathematics phobia, implying that fear of math leads to delays in completing academic tasks. Similarly, Rabins (2021) discovered a significant link between test phobia and academic procrastination among secondary school students in Kenya. The findings showed that students with higher levels of test phobia were more prone to procrastinate, demonstrating the powerful role of anxiety in delaying academic work. This relationship was further supported by Akinsola and Tella (2007), whose study in Jordan revealed a similar pattern among university students, with test phobia being strongly associated with academic procrastination. Longjohn and Michael-Olomu (2019) also examined how psychosocial factors, including self-efficacy and locus of control, influence procrastination. While self-efficacy had a weaker relationship with procrastination, external factors such as locus of control, gender, and marital status were stronger predictors. Overall, the studies collectively suggest that phobias, particularly related to academic tasks, can significantly contribute to procrastination, and counseling services should be provided to manage these issues effectively.

The joint contribution of depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia to academic procrastination among University of Ibadan Distance Learning Students in Oyo State, Nigeria was significant, as shown by the correlation coefficient ($R = 0.749$, $p < 0.05$). This result indicates that 54.6% ($\text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.546$) of the variance in procrastination was accounted for by the linear combination of these independent variables. Each variable contributed significantly to academic procrastination, with depression emerging as the most potent contributor, followed by burnout, anxiety and phobia. These findings suggest that emotional and psychological challenges, particularly depression and anxiety, play a substantial role in influencing procrastination behaviors among distance learning students. While phobia was the least significant predictor, its contribution still reflects that fears and anxieties related to academic tasks can exacerbate procrastination. This highlights the importance of addressing these psychological factors in intervention strategies, as reducing their impact could lead to lower levels of procrastination. The study recommends counseling services for students to help manage these emotional and psychological issues effectively, thereby reducing procrastination and improving academic outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia are significant determinants of procrastination among distance learning students, emphasizing the need for counseling services to address these psychological challenges. Interventions targeting these factors could help students manage procrastination more effectively and improve their academic outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the study's findings:

- Universities, particularly distance learning centers, should provide comprehensive counseling services to help students manage psychological challenges such as depression, anxiety, burnout, and phobia. Regular mental health check-ins and workshops can promote well-being and reduce procrastination tendencies.
- Institutions should offer workshops on time management and stress reduction techniques tailored to the needs of distance learning students. These workshops can help students cope with academic pressures and prevent the onset of procrastination due to anxiety or burnout.
- Creating peer support groups where students can share experiences and coping strategies may help mitigate feelings of isolation, depression, or burnout. Support groups can foster a sense of community and accountability, helping students stay on track with their academic work.
- Universities should develop easily accessible online resources, such as self-help tools, relaxation exercises, and mental health assessments, specifically designed for distance learners. These resources can offer immediate support for students experiencing psychological distress.
- Mental health awareness and coping strategies should be integrated into the academic curriculum, helping students identify early signs of depression, anxiety, and burnout, and providing them with tools to manage these challenges alongside their studies.
- Academic advisors should collaborate with students to create individualized support plans that accommodate their mental health needs. These plans could include flexible deadlines, personalized study schedules, and strategies to manage procrastination, especially for students experiencing severe depression or anxiety.

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